

Report

OCEAN DATA SURVEY SWEDEN 2023

CHALLENGES, TRENDS, AND TECHNOLOGIES

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Introduction

This report aims to highlight the trends, technologies, and challenges in using ocean data in Sweden in 2023. The report summarizes responses to an online survey conducted 5 December 2023 to 15 January 2024. The survey was anonymous and contained 32 multiple choice questions.

The entire data set is available from the Swedish National Data Service:

Ocean Data Factory Sweden. (2024). *Ocean Data Survey Sweden 2023 - Survey response data*. University of Gothenburg. <https://doi.org/10.5878/agvb-9w53>

The Ocean Data Survey Sweden is produced by Swedish National Data Service and data science consultancy Combine AB, together with Chalmers University of Technology and University of Gothenburg, within the collaboration of Ocean Data Factory Sweden (ODF Sweden). For more information about ODF Sweden, please visit oceansdatafactory.se.

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Key Findings

Respondents and their organizations

Respondents included individuals from government (44%), industry (28%), independent (20%), research (12%) and academia (8%) from a relatively balanced spread of organization sizes. The vast majority (96%) are based in Sweden or working with Swedish data. Q1 Q2 Q3

64% of organizations had an advanced or intermediate level of data maturity, and 76% of organizations worked extensively or frequently with ocean data. Q4 Q5

Respondents were heavily weighted towards having extensive *general* data experience, with 48% having over 15 years of experience, and another 24% with more than 8 years of experience. However, the transition to working with ocean data is a recent one for many respondents. Q8 Q9 Q10

Data collection and ingestion

88% of respondents' organisations have collected ocean data although 36% do not know how much ocean data are collected by their organization per year. 48 % respond that data collection is the most time-consuming ocean data task in their organisation. Q11 Q16 Q29

Many organisations collect data regularly, but there is a large spread among the collection frequencies, from streaming (16%) to annually (8%). 32% organisations collect data on an ad hoc / irregular basis. Time series data (75%) and images/video (64%) are the most frequently gathered data. Q13 Q15

There is a near-equal split between those who collect their own data versus those using external sources. The Swedish service SMHI is listed as the preferred external data provider (68%), followed by international providers EMODnet and Copernicus (36%). Q12 Q17

32% of the organizations collected high (29%) or very high (3%) sensitivity ocean data. Q14

Most respondents store their ocean data on external hard drives or local devices (42%) or on-premise servers (21%). Only 17 % of respondents store their data in the cloud. Q19

Data analysis and usage

Most respondents conduct activities related to data summarization (68 %) and cleaning (52%). Tabular data (65%), GIS data (61%), image data (52%) and video data (43%) are the most used. Q18 Q20

Data collection was listed as the most time-consuming ocean data task (48%), followed by data processing (22%), data cleaning (13%), and analysis (13%). Q29

Excel is the most commonly-used application for ocean data analysis (64%), followed by Python and QGIS (56%) and ArcGis (44%). Matlab was listed by only 16 % of the respondents. Analysing ocean data with desktop applications was more common than with automated processes. Q21

The main organizational goals for analyzing ocean data were evenly spread across surveying (52%), identifying trends and patterns (56%), species/environmental monitoring

(52%), informing decision-making/planning (52%), predictive modelling and forecasting (44%). Q23

Organisations often (46% of respondents) only publish collected ocean data infrequently or only on request, but some (25% of respondents) organisations publish regularly. Q26

For those that do publish, the main target audience is external stakeholders (42%). 43% organisations have a way (API or dedicated infrastructure) of sharing their data, but 29% of the organizations have no way of sharing their data with others. Q25 Q27

All organizations generate some type of outputs that represent easily interpreted summaries of datasets (reports and dashboards, visualizations, processed images and videos, geospatial data outputs, reports, time series data). Only 24% of organizations produce processed data sets. Q28

Use of AI/ML

The use of ML and AI techniques when dealing with ocean data was low as no respondent indicated that they used these extensively. Indeed 36 % of respondents indicated that they used these somewhat or very little while 28% reported not at all using them. Q22

As for potential use cases of AI in their organization's data applications based on current needs, responses covered most application areas, perhaps an indication that respondents believed that AI could generally help with any task in areas such as Automated Data Analysis, Marine Species Identification and Predictive Modelling. Q24

Challenges

When *dealing* with ocean data, regulation was reported by a majority (52%) of the respondents as one of the biggest challenges affecting their organisations, and lack of data by almost as many (48%). Q30

When *looking* for ocean data, data accessibility is reported as one of the main challenges experienced by organisations (52%), followed by a lack of standardisation and metadata (43%) and data security / privacy (39%). Q31

When it comes to issues affecting the organizations, regulatory changes were noted by 48% of the respondents, with emerging technologies (39%) and advancements in data analytics (35%) following. Cybersecurity threats was noted only by 17% of the respondents, and only 4% noted competition from changing market dynamics, suggesting that most organisations do not feel market pressures as particularly relevant. Q32

Focussing in on: What characterizes organisations that regularly publish ocean data?

Six people responded that their organizations regularly publish data, defined here as at least once a year (5 respondents) or continuously (1). Five of these are medium or large (>50 employees) Government or Academic organizations, the other one a micro (<5 employees) Industry organization. All these organizations responded that they rely on external providers for ocean data to-at-least-an-equal extent to collecting their own data, although it is not clear whether the externally-provided or own-collected data then becomes published. Perhaps surprisingly, three of the organizations responded that the data their organizations collect have moderate or high sensitivity. Again, though, it is not clear whether the sensitive data is published, or whether the published data is lower sensitivity.

Perhaps most surprising is that there appears to be a clear distinction between the amount of processing that these organizations perform on collected data compared to organizations that publish data infrequently or on request. Of the six respondents from organizations that regularly publish data, two responded that their organizations did not perform any of the listed processing activities, and three listed only one activity (Aggregation and summarization, or Data cleaning and preprocessing). These five organizations were the medium or large Government or Academic organizations, whereas the micro-industry organization and 10 of the 11 respondents whose organizations publish data irregularly listed 3 or even 4 processing activities.

These results point to an ocean data accessibility “ecosystem” in Sweden in which government organizations play a crucial role as data aggregators and publishers, sourcing external data and making it available through dedicated infrastructure. The heavy reliance on aggregator services to obtain data (SMHI/SHARK/SHARKweb, EMODnet and Copernicus) rather than data repositories (SND) and self-hosted solutions (e.g. an organization’s own webpages, which would be categorized as Other) further supports this characterization.

We hypothesize that the organizations whose respondents stated their organization infrequently published data are probably feeding these aggregator services, as four out of five responded they have an easy way to share data, with three responding they have dedicated infrastructure for the purpose.

One possible complication to this interpretation is that the questionnaire did not explicitly define what was meant by “to publish” data. Some respondents may have interpreted “publish” in a strict sense as meaning “to make data available directly” to the public, and thus have not considered providing data privately to aggregator organizations as “publishing”. In future ocean data surveys, we might consider rewording the question to explicitly focus on the final accessibility of the data that organizations collect, to remove this ambiguity.

Result

Limitations

The survey targeted individuals. The responses are subjective self-assessments, not necessarily corresponding with the official view of the organisations these individuals work at. Twenty-five individuals responded, a few choosing not to respond all questions. The percentage values stated in this report were calculated using the number of responses for each question individually.

Organisations

Q1: Is your organisation based in Sweden and/or work with Swedish data? (collection, ingestion, processing, analysis, usage, output)

Yes.	23
No.	1

Q2: What is the size of your company / institution / organization?

Q3: Which group most accurately describes your organisation?

Q4: What best describes the general data maturity of your organisation?

Q5: To what extent does your organisation work with ocean data?

Q6: Which of the following best describes the typical ocean environment (distance from shore, Sweden or outside of Sweden) of the ocean data which your organization work with?

(In the next survey this question will be separated into two: Distance from shore, and Swedish/non-Swedish water.)

Users

Q7: Which role best describes you in relation to ocean data in your organisation?

Q8: Approximately how many years of experience with data *in general* do you have (in both current and previous positions)?

less than 3 years	1
3 - 8 years	6
8 - 15 years	6
more than 15 years	12

Q9: Approximately how many years of experience with *ocean* data do you have (in both current and previous positions)?

less than 3 years	5
3 - 8 years	7
8 - 15 years	5
more than 15 years	8

Q10: Select the programming languages you consider yourself proficient in: (Select all that apply)

Data collection & ingestion

Q11: Does your organisation collect ocean data?

Yes.	21
No, but we have collected data in the past.	1
No, we have never collected data.	3

Q12: To what extent does your organisation rely on collecting its own ocean data versus using external providers?

We collect our own ocean data exclusively.	4
We mostly collect our own ocean data but also use external providers.	6
We equally rely on collecting our own ocean data and using external providers.	6
We mostly rely on external providers but also collect some ocean data internally.	5
We exclusively rely on external providers for our ocean data.	4

Q13: What typically describes the frequency of the ocean data collection of your organisation?

Q14: How sensitive (e.g., in terms of national security, GDPR) is the ocean data your organisation collects?

Q15: What is the main type of ocean data your organisation collects?

Q16: How much ocean data is collected by your organisation per year? (roughly)

Q17: When looking for ocean data externally, which are your preferred data providers? (Select all that apply)

Data processing, analysis, and usage.

Q18: Which of the following processing activities does your organization typically perform on collected ocean data? (Select all that apply)

Q19: Where is your ocean data typically stored?

Q20: Which data format do you typically use when analysing ocean data?

Q21: Which of the following is most commonly used for ocean data analysis in your organisation? (Select all that apply)

Q22: Has your organisation used machine learning / AI techniques when dealing with ocean data?

(Note that the answer "Extensively" was not selected by anyone.)

Q23: What are the main goals when analysing ocean data inside your organisation?
(Select all that apply)

Surveying.	13
Identifying trends and patterns.	14
Species / environmental monitoring.	13
Compliance and regulatory reporting.	5
Informing decision-making / planning.	13
Predictive modeling and forecasting.	11
Other.	2

Q24: What do you see as the potential use case(s) for AI in your organisation's ocean data applications based on its current needs?

Data Quality Control.	8
Automated Data Analysis.	15
Autonomous Data Collection.	10
Marine Species Identification.	12
Climate Change Impact Assessment.	9
Predictive modeling.	12
Enhanced Decision Support.	9
Real-time Monitoring.	11
Integration with Other Technologies.	10

Data Outputs

Q25: What is the main target audience for your data?

Q26: Does your organization publish any of the ocean data it collects?

We regularly publish a wide range of data (at least once a year).	5
We infrequently publish data.	5
We publish specific datasets on request.	6
We do not publish data at all.	7
Other.	1

Q27: Does your organization offer an easy way to share its ocean data?

Yes, by a well-established API for data sharing.	3
Yes, by a dedicated infrastructure for data sharing via services, such as file transfer.	7
No, but access can be granted by request, e.g. via e-mail.	4
No, we do not have any way of granting access to our data.	7
Other.	2

Q28: Which of the following best describe the typical data outputs from your organisation? (Select all that apply)

Data Challenges

Q29: Which ocean data tasks are the most time-consuming in your organisation?

Q30: What are the biggest challenges facing your organisation when dealing with ocean data? (Select all that apply)

Q31: What are the main challenges you experience when looking for ocean data?
(Select all that apply)

Data Accessibility.	12
Data Silos / Fragmentation.	6
Spatial / Temporal Resolution.	5
Data Quality.	7
Lack of metadata / standardization.	10
Limited coverage of region of interest.	7
Data Security / Privacy.	9
Data Cost.	5
Data Interoperability.	3
Other.	2

Q32: Which of the following are currently affecting your organisation / field most in relation to ocean data? (Select all that apply)

Advancements in data analytics and artificial intelligence.	8
Regulatory changes impacting data privacy and security.	11
Emerging technologies and data collection methods.	9
Increased competition and changing market dynamics.	1
Evolving customer expectations and demands.	5
Cybersecurity threats and data breaches.	4
Integration of big data and Internet of Things (IoT).	5
Changes in data governance and compliance standards.	6
Other.	2